

Review Article

Wisdom: Key Requirement for a Sustainable Development of a Nation

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Abstract

Sustainable development is the concept that individuals and societies must live and satisfy their requirements without jeopardizing future generations' capacity to cope using its own resources. One of the concepts is wisdom. In this paper, the holy bible was used as the major reference. The ways by which wisdom is endowed unto a nation and the benefits of applying of God's wisdom were discussed.

Keyword: Wisdom, society, Holy bible, Holy Spirit, God, Daniel, Christian religion.

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Introduction

The Concept of Sustainable Development

This is the satisfaction of human needs and aspiration in the major objective development. The essential needs of people in development (food, clothing, shelter, jobs) are not being met and beyond their basic needs these people have legitimate aspiration for an improved quality of life (Meier, 1991). A world in which poverty and inequality are endemic will always be prone to ecological and other crises.

The principal developmental challenge is to meet the needs and aspiration of an expanding developing world population.

God's wisdom

Wisdom is the ability to discern or judge what is true, right or lasting. For a nation to sustainably develop the citizenry needs it.

To effectively discuss on this topic, I have tried to divide it into parts which I think would contribute to physical and spiritual knowledge.

THE WAYS BY WHICH WISDOM IS ENDOWED UNTO A NATION

i. **Given by God.** Wisdom is the principal thing; therefore get wisdom and with all thy getting get understanding. Exalt her and she shall promote thee (Prov 4:7-12. God almighty is the custodian of wisdom. He has commanded that anybody who needs it should ask and it shall be given unto him. Anybody that has God's wisdom is wise and any nation that embraces it is a wise nation. The wise shall inherit glory, but shame shall be the promotion of fools. (Prov3:35). A wise nation that embraces wisdom shall inherit God's glory meaning her development will be rapid.

The Lord said to Moses see I have appointed Bazel and have filled him with the spirit of God, giving him great wisdom. (Ex 31:1-3). A good leader should ask for wisdom like Solomon did (1King3:11-14; Eccl2:24-26; Act 6:10;7: 10).

ii. **It can be sought for:**

Eph5:15-16, 2Tim 3:15; James 3:13-17.

Jealousy and selfishness are not God's kind of wisdom. Such things are earthy, unspiritual, inspired by the devil. For wherever there is jealousy or selfish ambition, there will be disorder and every other kind of evil.

It is therefore needed for people of a nation to sought for wisdom of being wise so as to avoid bitterness, jealousy, selfishness because these are of the devil. A nation that engages in things of the devil will definitely suffer under development.

iii. **Through Holy Spirit**

Not all men are entitled to the acquisition of wisdom, meaning that not all men are wise. It is through the power of the Holy Spirit somebody can give acquire it.

Isa 11:2; and the spirit of the Lord shall rest upon him, the spirit of wisdom, understanding, counsel and might; the spirit of knowledge and fear of the Lord.

Jn 14: 2; but when the father send the comforter instead of me and by the comforter I mean the holy spirit, he will teach you much.

Jn 16;13; when the holy spirit who is truth, comes, he shall guide you into all truth, to one person the spirit gives the ability to give wise advise.....

1Cor 12:8; anybody who needs wisdom should try as much as possible to be empowered first with the power of Holy Spirit the source of wisdom.

Examples of those who applied wisdom.

1. Leaders

- (i) Jesus Christ ; wear my yoke- for it fits perfectly and let me teach you for I am gentle and humble and you shall find rest for your souls...(Matt 11:29-30). Here Jesus Christ demonstrated he's wisdom with gentleness, humility, humbleness.
- (ii) Solomon ; 1King3:9; give me an understanding mind so that I can govern your people well...because you have asked for wisdom in governing people, and haven't asked for a long life or richer for yourself...

Solomon was great in wisdom and understanding his wisdom excelled that of the wise men of east including those in Egypt. He wrote 1005 songs and authors 3000 proverbs. To crown it all kings from many land sent their ambassador to him for advice (1King4:29-34). He was rich, a good judge, built temple in Jerusalem for 40years.

2. Joseph

Joseph came to a land of Egypt a captive found by Ishmaelite trader, he was purchased from them by Potiphar a member of the personal staff of pharaoh, the king of Egypt (Gen19:1). He was blessed in his master's house so that everything he did was successful; this made him to lead everybody in household.

He applied wisdom in the following ways;

Gen 39:7 Potiphar's wife began making eyes at Joseph, and suggested that he came and sleep with her and joseph refused 'look' he told her 'my master trust me with everything in the entire Household' This is wisdom.

Gen 41: Joseph interpreted Pharaoh's dream and he was made the governor.

39... 'Since God has revealed the meaning of the dreams to you, you are the WISEST man in the country'

40: 'I hereby appoint you to be in charge of this entire project''

He was thirty years old as he entered the service of the king during those years, Joseph re .. for the government a portion of all the crops grown throughout Egypt, strong them in early cities . When there was severe famine all over world, Joseph opened up the storehouse and sold the grains to those who cares to buy. (Gen 41:46-57). This was wisdom which any nation should try to copy.

iii) Prince of Tyre.

Prince of Tyre was a wise prince he had used wisdom and understanding to get great wealth of many treasure (Ezekiel 28; 4-5), unfortunately, he was very PROUD and he was punished for it 'therefore the lord God says; because you claim that you are as wise as God, an enemy army, the terror of the nations, shall suddenly draw their swords against your marvelous wisdom and defile your splendor' - Ezekiel28; 6-7.

iv) King David

3. Individuals who exhibited wisdom.

To make this write up to be more explicit I will make few examples of individuals who exhibited the wisdom given to them.

(i) A woman intercedes for Absalom.

For a nation to be great, there is the need for intercessors who pray always without ceasing. Here is an example of a woman from Telcoa who interceded for the return of Absalom who was banished to a place called Creshur. (2 Sam 14:124)

Verse 1-2.. he sent for a woman of Telcoa who after the women confronted the king. He eventually agreed that Absalom should be brought back to Jerusalem (vs 23).

Wise men and bride maid.

Reading from the authorized King James Version of the bible there was a reference to wise men from the east to Jerusalem who visited King Herod they announced the birth of Jesus Christ- king of Jewa (Matt2:1-3)

Vs 1.... Behold there came wise men from the east to Jerusalem. Vs2.... Where is he that is born king of the Jews? For we have seen his star in the east, and have come to worship him.

ii) Bridesmaids: Matthew 25:1-4

iii) **Daniel**

King Nebuchadnezzar of Babylon fought and conquered Judah thereby confiscating their properties. Among them are children in whom was no blemish, but well favoured, and skillful in all wisdom, and winning in knowledge to stand in the king's palace, and whom they might teach the learning and the tongue of the Chaldeans (Daniel1:4).

Among them are Daniel, Hananiah, Mischael and Azaniah. Daniel purposed in his heart that he would not defile himself with the portion of the king's meat nor with the wine which he drank.

1 vs. 17 'as for these four children, God gave them knowledge and skill in all learning and wisdom: and Daniel had understanding in all vision and dreams. 1 vs 20 ' and in all matters of wisdom and understanding that the king enquired of them, he found them ten times better than all the magicians and astrologer that were in all his realm.

5 vs 14 '....., that the spirit of the gods is in thee, and that light and understanding and excellent wisdom is found in thee'.

With the wisdom, God empowered Daniel with, he was useful for King Belshazzar by interpreting the handwriting on the wall 'MENE, MENE, TEKEL, UPHARSIN. The interpretation brought him promotion to the position of the third tier in the kingdom. If not for the God's wisdom the riddle of handwriting would not have been solved and no promotion would have been earned.

It is critically recommended that for a nation to be sustainably developed; there is the need to make use of the "Daniels" in the helm of affairs of a nation. Excellence wisdom is needed in any development in life.

In the book of James 3:13-17, it reads thus:

Vs 13 ' who is a wise man and endued with knowledge among you' Let him shew out a good conversation his works with meekness of wisdom'.

Vs 15 ' this wisdom descended not from above, but is earthly, sensual, devilish' Vs 16 ' for where envying and strife is, there is confusion and every evil work'.

Verses 14-15 critically show that God's wisdom is the ultimate for a nation to be sustainably developed. V 16 shows that any wisdom that does not come from God's there are problems erupting wherever they applied. Brethren for a country, nation, home, work place to develop. God's wisdom is the principal thing needed.

MENTOR AND MENTEES

Mentors are leaders/founder of a church who ought to teach the mentees, while the latter is a student/ learner who is to learn from the former (Anozie, 2013). It is a master and followership relationship. If a mentor has to record a success on the outcome of his expected duties on his subordinates he has to have God's wisdom and vice versa.

I have enumerated on those who obtained and applied God's wisdom in their understandings. They were successful in the roles assigned to them. Now I will also do justice to the issue of mentors and mentees.

(i) Elijah and Elisha relationship

God commanded Elijah to anoint Elisha who is to take over him as a prophet (1 King 19:15-16). Elijah went and a cloud came as commanded since then Elisha has been following him as his assistant (1 King 19:21). During the course of their relationship we saw how they have been using God's wisdom in dealing with each other as a boss and servant.

We saw how Elisha demonstrated God's wisdom when the time came for the Lord to take Elijah to heaven by means of a whirlwind. Elijah said to Elisha as they left Gilgal "stay here, for the Lord has told me to go to Bethel. But Elisha replied I won't leave you.... These words were repeated three times at different places during the course of their journey.

Finally, a chariot of fire, drawn by horses of fire appeared and drove between them, separating them, and Elijah was carried by a whirlwind into heaven. As they disappeared from his sight he (Elisha) tore his (Elijah) robe (2 King 2:12). If not for God's wisdom Elisha used, he would have missed twice as much prophetic power Elijah gave to him.

(ii) Elisha and Gehazi relationship

Elisha and Gehazi relationship is that of a 'boss' and servant (2 King 4:12).

Gehazi is a servant who did not apply God's wisdom in his dealing with Elisha. The trust is not there he quarries, doubts a lot and self-centered. It was opposite of Elijah and Elisha relationship.

The action that broke the camel's back was when Naaman, commander-in chief of king of Syria army visited Elisha. He complained of leprosy. Elisha commanded him to "wash in the Jordan river seven times and he was healed when he yielded to the command (2king 5; 14).

Vs. 14 'so Naaman went down to the Jordan River and dipped himself seven times, as the prophet had told him to. And his flesh became as healthy as a little child and he was healed.

Naaman used God's wisdom here; if not so he would have remained a leper. Naaman tried to compensate Elisha for the healing, but Elisha refused it, but Gehazi's converted the gift by stealing it. Elisha did not like the idea. He caused Gehazi (2king5; 27).

'Because you have done thus, Naaman's leprosy shall be upon you and upon your children and your children's children forever.'

(iii) Elisha and the officer assisting the king.

There was famine in Samaria. Elisha was brought before the king. The king said 'the lord has caused this mess' why should I expect any help from him/' Elisha replied, 'the lord says that by this time of tomorrow two gallons of barley of flour or flour gallons of barley grain will be sold in the markets of Samaria for a dollar.

The officer assisting the king said, 'that couldn't happen if the Lord made windows in the sky!' and the prophets had said 'you will see it happen' but you won't be able to buy any of it (vs. 19). It happened when the Syrians abounded their goods which included food. 'And he couldn't, for the people trample him to death at the gate (vs 20).

(iv) Samuel and Eli Relationship

(v) Judges

Throughout the period of Israel's history there is a tragic cycle observed, that of rebellion against God, followed by the judgment of God, usually in the form of foreign invasion. The children of Israel then cry to God for help and a 'judge' was sent to save them. During the discharge of the Judge duty. God has been their leader and they followed. God directs by speaking and commanding them.

These individual leaders called judges used God's wisdom in the discharge of their duties. They never went to wars without God's directives. It should be noted that when everybody does his own thing without God's wisdom there is always chaos and dysfunction.

Examples of the judges: it is worthy to note these few judges who performed excellently well by their leadership roles in.

1. Deborah - (Judges 4&5)
2. Gideon - (Judges 6-8) 3.
- Jephtha- (Judges 11-12).

1a. Divine wisdom is given to man by God, but there is also human wisdom, or common sense. The first step to wisdom is to trust and reverence the Lord. This is to say that only when a man trusts in God's will he be truly wise. Human wisdom is good and necessary but no matter how skilled a person is, without humility in the presence of God and a willingness to learn from him, he will inevitably go astray.

Blessings received when God's wisdom is applied.

(i) Wise men

Prov 1vs 5-6 'I want those already wise to become wiser and become leaders....how can someone become a wise man? The answer is in vs. 7-9 '... the first step is to trust and reverence the Lord'.

(ii) Good Judgment

The men who know right from wrong and have good judgment and common sense is happier than the man who is immensely rich (prov3:13).

(iii) Blessings

(a) Long good life (prov3:1-6) (b) Riches (prov8:18) (c) honor (prov4:18) (d) pleasure (e) peace (prov16:7) (f) inheritance (prov3:15-17; Ecc 7:11) of God's glory (g) Good and happy home (h) exploits (i) ornament of grace.

(iv) Deut 28:1-4

There is the need for faithfulness and obedience to God's command. God who blessed the Israelites in the past can still do it again. There is the need to apply wisdom in all undertakings.

Vs 1 'if you fully obey all these commandments of the Lord your God' Vs 2 'these are the blessings that will come upon you: blessing in the city, blessing in the field'.

THE OUTCOME OF APPLICATION OF GOD'S WISDOM

- a. Blessed city/nation
- b. Blessed field(bountiful harvest)
- c. Victory at war front
- d. Living the life of holiness
- e. Blessed with good children
- f. Good weather
- g. Lending to nations
- h. Promotions (head not tail).

Anybody or nation that does not reference or obey God shall definitely reap the opposite of these blessings which is 'curse' (Deut 28; 15-17).

Important Quotations

Proverbs 8 & 9

Vs 1-3 'can't you hear the voice of wisdom? she is standing at the city gates and at every fork in the road, and at the door of every house. Listen to what she says.'

Vs 11-12 'for the value of wisdom is far above rubies: nothing can be compared with it'

11-15 'wisdom, give good and vice and commonsense. Because of my strength kings reign in power. I show the judges who is right and who is wrong.'

21' those who love and follow me are indeed wealthy. I fill their treasures'

33 'listen to my counsel-oh don't refuse if I and be wise.

9 vs 9 'teach a wise man and he will be the wiser. Teach a good man and he will learn more.'

10 'for the reverence and fear of God are basic to all wisdom. Knowing God results in every other kind of understanding.

11 'wisdom will make the hours of yours days more profitable and the years of your life more fruitful'

10 vs 28 'trust in your money and down you go. 'Trust in God and flourish as a tree'

14 vs 1 'A wise woman builds her house while a foolish woman tears hers down by her own efforts'

Conclusion

Jesus Christ 28:19-20 has mandated the nation (church) to go and teach all nations. Therefore the role of the church is to teach people, the Holy bible would be used as a guide. This prayer contribution is teaching all nationalities to grab hold of God's wisdom, be it leaders and subjects by this, there would be a meaningful national development.

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